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Assessment of Internet Facilities usage on Reading Culture among Wesley High School Students in Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study assessed internet facilities usage on reading culture among Wesley high school students in Otukpo, Benue state, Nigeria. Three objectives guided the study. The research design adopted was a survey research design. The population of the study comprised of 278 SS2 and SS3 students of the school studied in 2023/2024 academic session. The sampling technique used was a complete census. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire titled: "Impact of Internet Facilities on Student's Reading Culture Questionnaire (IIFSRCQ)". The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validity. The reliability score of the questionnaire was 87.53 Cronbach Alpha Value. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, simple percentages and mean scores. The findings showed that majority of the students make use of the internet to study, prepare for examinations, write assignments, and chatting with friends, among others. Making the students active in class, distracting their reading, and exposing them to unimportant articles and write-ups were among the perceived impact. The study recommended that Management of secondary schools should organize seminars aimed at teaching the students the right use of the internet to improve their reading culture, among other things.

Keywords: Reading, Reading Culture, Internet, impact, Student.

Introduction

Reading is the springboard of any literacy program. It is one of the oldest habits of human civilization and has remained the passion of the greatest personalities of all times. According to Nnadozie and Egwim (2010), reading is a complex skill requiring the coordination of several inter related sources of information. It is the art of interpreting printed and written words, and the most effective process of conscious learning, which influences the extent and accuracy of information as well as the attitudes, morals, beliefs, judgement and action of individuals (Edeole & Adejoke, 2016).

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However, due to the attitude of individuals who rarely pick a book or magazine to read, there is a serious decline in reading culture. The same applies to the schoolchild for whom reading has come to mean a thing of spare time. Considering the place of creative thinking in reading, it becomes very important for one to develop the rudiments of reading and the culture of reading always. The importance of reading culture cannot be overemphasized because it is crucial for both personal and academic success. Furthermore, it is an aid to language development, socialization and civilization.

The development of good reading culture is important because society has realized the importance of information and effective communication for the survival and exploitation of their environment. Moreover, the development of reading and reading culture are basic skills, which society must confer on its students as part of their childhood education. Unfortunately, there are problems inherent in the development of proper reading culture among students because of some technological innovations. One of the technological innovations is the Internet. The Internet can be broadly defined as a worldwide network of computers communicating through an approved protocol. The Internet according to Kumar and Kaur in Jibrin, Musa and Shittu (2017), has an unlimited wealth of information resources that are readily available and easily accessible for people to use worldwide and simultaneously. Internet is a veritable tool in learning, teaching and research if effectively used. However, it has been observed that owing to this technological innovation, reading culture is being threatened, especially, among teens and secondary school students (Yusuf, 2015).

In Nigerian society today, while technology is slowly taking a steady control over individual lives, the reading culture among secondary school students is fast vanishing. Today, students rather than read to acquire new knowledge prefer to spend hours unending, surfing the net, playing with funky handsets, chatting and passing non-stop short message services (SMSs), thereby making reading a book or any other information resource in a quiet or peaceful corner of a library or home an archaic idea. The declining interest in reading among our children (especially those in secondary schools) compared to increase in hours spent on the Internet has become a cause for alarm and a challenge to all and something needs to be done to change the scenario. However, assuming or concluding that Internet use is the cause of the declining reading culture can be better regarded as an assumption until empirically proven. It is against this backdrop that the current study is assessing internet facilities usage

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on reading culture among Wesley high school students in Otukpo, Benue state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid advancement of internet technology has transformed how students access and engage with information. While the internet provides vast resources that can enhance learning, its usage also raises concerns about its impact on students' reading culture. In Wesley High School, Otukpo, Benue State, there is growing concern that students may be shifting from traditional reading habits, such as reading textbooks, novels, and academic materials, to spending more time on social media, online gaming, and entertainment websites. Despite the availability of internet facilities in the school and among students, little is known about how these resources are being utilized and whether they contribute positively or negatively to students' reading culture. Some researchers argue that the internet can enhance reading habits through access to e-books, online journals, and educational blogs, while others believe that it distracts students and reduces their engagement with academic texts (Musa & Shittu, 2017; Yusuf, 2017). This study seeks to assess the usage of internet facilities and its impact on the reading culture of students in Wesley High School Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, it aims to determine whether internet access promotes or hinders reading habits, identify the types of online content students engage with, and explore possible ways to enhance the positive effects of internet usage on reading culture. Addressing this issue is essential to ensuring that the internet serves as a tool for academic growth rather than a distraction from meaningful reading practices.

Research objectives

The study is guided by the following objectives, which involve, to:

1. Find out if students of Wesley high school Otukpo make use of the Internet facilities
2. Determine the students' reasons for their use of the Internet facilities
3. Investigate the perceived impact of the Internet facilities by the students on their reading culture

Research questions

1. Do students of Wesley high school Otukpo make use of the Internet facilities?
2. What are the students' reasons for their use of the Internet facilities?

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3. What is the perceived impact of the Internet facilities by the students on their reading culture?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the students' reasons for use of internet facilities and students on their reading culture

Literature review

Since the advent of ICT, the subject of the students' reading culture has attracted a major concern. According to Yusuf (2015), this major concern is because of the need to keep the schoolchild active and able to cope with the demands of the present day. In the same vein, Saka, Bitagi, and Garba (2012) pointed out that inculcating a reading culture should be introduced at an early age among children. This is because reading and reading culture develop over a prolonged period and an early promotion will be able to mold them into lifelong readers. The challenge is therefore to ingrain the culture of reading in children so that it is as important as sports and other hobbies. Perhaps then, the impact of negative media will be directly reduced. Furthermore, Yani (2003) observed that reading culture of Nigerians is a matter of concern in our educational and national development, stating further that in a developing country like Nigeria, the concept of reading culture should not be relegated to the background.

Fundamentally, the major way to improve the reading culture of students is through a well-equipped school library. Topo, as cited in Strong (2014) affirmed that the need today is the thoughtful integration of book reading with high technology, as it will reverse the decline in book reading among children and adults. In addition, Yusuf (2007) asserted that equipping school libraries is the first practical step in these efforts. This is because books and other information resources are the most suitable medium through which knowledge is transmitted from generation to generation.

Nonetheless, Kristy (as cited in Kolawole, 2005) reported that the prevalence of poor reading skills varies, and believed the consequential effect to include poor grades for students and difficulty trying to find or advance to a good job for adults. Saka, Bitagi and Garba (2012) in their submission were of the view that the majority of students read to pass examinations and to do assignments. The implication being that absence of examinations and assignments creates a distance between students and their books, while shifting their attention and energy to the net for frivolities. As to what these students prefer, the study of Chen, Hsiao, Chern and Chen (as cited in Almasi,

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Machumu & Zhu, 2017) reported a growing increase in the use of the Internet, which is gradually eroding reading culture among secondary school students.

The authors, however, observed that the students use the Internet also for activities related to schoolwork as well as more General activities, believing that Internet-based activities in schools may have several impacts on students` life at schools and thereafter. Besides, various studies have reported that the use of the internet can have benefits on the educational achievement of students.

Considering the influence of the use of the Internet on student learning performance or other outcomes, the studies of Davis (2001), Widyanto and Griffiths (2006), Odaci and Kalkkan (2010), and Odaci (2011) reported that it has either a negative influence or no significant influence. Furthermore, Young (as cited in Amasi et al., 2017) suggested that excessive internet usage among students have negative effects on students` academic success.

The studies of Olatokun (2008) and Nwagwu, Adekannbi and Bello (2008) reported that students chiefly utilize the Internet for academic purposes, such as preparation for assignments and examinations, rather than for leisure purposes. Though some students use the Internet much more than their school libraries, they also find the Internet as a source of general knowledge since it assists them in their reading habits as well as improving their academic performances.

Tarimo and Kavishe (2017), believed that by providing Internet access and enhancing its usage in schools, a chance to improve students` learning through access to the huge amount of information that is accessible on the internet is guaranteed.

Chen and Fu (2009) stated that the Internet has brought unparalleled opportunities to students on one hand and a major concern for parents on the other hand. This is because while online searching for information helps to boost examination scores and performances in assignments given to students, using the internet mainly for socializing and gaming results in poor reading habit and poor performance in examinations, general academic achievements as well as poor personal development. Since some internet use may seriously distract students, affect their reading habit and generally distort their academic achievements, students should employ effective use of the Internet.

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In the same vein, the studies of Adedotun (as cited in Yebowaah, 2018); Akande and Bamise (2017) reported that access to information brought about by the use of the Internet can influence the academic performance of the secondary school students. Also, Sahin, Balta and Ercan (2010) and Yebowaah (2018) believed that the use of credible Internet resources is of greater importance for academic activity, especially in high-class courses which require an academic review of the literature. This is not different from the belief of Kim (as cited in Yebowaah, 2018) who asserted that Internet use for educational purpose is the heart of adolescent academic achievement, as it helps students to broaden their academic knowledge, research and assignments by accessing information worldwide as well as enhances easy communication to the academic community.

On what needs to be done to avoid the negative influence of the Internet on the students, Chen *et al* as cited in Almasi, Machumu & Zhu (2017) noted that Internet usage is of benefit to students but believed that its negative use involves pornography addiction and excessive chat among secondary students, which have relatively negative effects on their academic success and life after school. In the same vein, Fuchs and Woessmann (2004); Kuhlemeier and Hemker (2007) believed that the Internet is used in daily life in educational settings; and as a result, its usage among secondary school students should be channeled appropriately to yield academic success.

Downes (2002) noted that if secondary-education teachers are to tailor their instruction to the needs of all students, they need to develop an understanding of the extent to which incoming students have access to and make use of the Internet at home. Campagna (as cited in Almasi *et al.*, 2017) emphasized that teachers should encourage students to come up with techniques for reading independently, which is one of the outcomes of reading habit.

In the same vein, Ngoumandjoka (as cited in Yebowaah, 2018) found that the Internet is not mostly used for academic purpose rather for recreational activities. The authors further buttressed that though students are more into the use of the Internet, in reality, they are using it mainly for non-academic purposes like emailing, gaming and social networking, which has contributed greatly to the decline in their reading culture. This brings to the fore the controversy among empirical studies on the influence of internet use on the academic performance and reading culture of secondary school students.

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Based on the literature review, it is clear that the Internet has serious effects on students and their reading culture. Students are so vulnerable to becoming addicted to the Internet to the extent that they do their homework not with their efforts but with complete dependence on Internet resources. This is to say that the influence of the Internet is in two faces, either negative or positive.

However, it would be inappropriate to conclude on the face the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State belong to. A critical look at available literature has revealed a gap in this respect, which forms the fulcrum of this research.

Methodology

The study was purely a descriptive survey because of the given large number of different sub-sets of the population involved. Thus, a descriptive survey design was adopted for the study owing to its usefulness in the field of computer Science. The population of the study was 278, which comprised senior secondary 2 and 3 classes (SS2 & SS3) in 2023/2024 academic session. Furthermore, the 278 students were sampled using the complete census sampling technique. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire titled: “Impact of Internet Facilities on Student’s Reading Culture Questionnaire (IIFSRCQ)”. The questionnaire was validated using face and content validation. The research instrument was validated by an expert in measurement and evaluation from the department of mathematics and Statistics in Federal University of Health Sciences Otukpo Benue State. Also, the instrument was distributed in Jesus College Otukpo Benue State for Pilot test among SS2 and SS3 students. A total of 50 copies of questionnaire was distributed to the students and retrieved. The data was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha. The overall Cronbach alpha value for the instrument was 87.53 which was found strong and reliable. Therefore, the instrument was used for the study. The items in the questionnaire consist of close-ended questions using four (4)-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. The data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, simple percentages and mean scores. A mid-point of 2.5 was taken as the acceptance criterion for the positive response. This implied that questionnaire items with a mean score of 2.5 and above denote “agreed” while questionnaire items with a mean score below 2.5 denote “disagreed”. Presentation of the result was done using the frequency tables.

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Presentation of Results

This section deals with the analysis of the outcomes of the data collected. A total of 278 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents but 275 copies were completed, returned and found useful for analysis. The presentation follows the order of the research objectives.

Research Objective 1: To find out if students of Wesley High school Otukpo make use of the Internet.

Table 1: Responses of the Students on the Use of Internet Facilities (N = 275)

S/N	Item statement	Yes	%	No	%
1	Do you make use of the Internet?	267	97.1	8	2.9

Source: Researcher's Field Survey

Table 1 shows the responses of the students on the use of the Internet. The result shows that the majority of the respondents 267(97.1%) indicated the use of the Internet, while few of the respondents that constitute 8(2.9%) indicated the non-use of the Internet. The result implies that students in Otukpo Local Government Area make use of the Internet.

This finding corroborates with the earlier studies carried out by Olatokun (2008), Tarimo and Kavishe (2017), which revealed the high use of the Internet among youths and secondary school students.

Research objective 2: To determine the students' reasons for their use of the Internet Facilities.

Table 2: Students' Reasons for Use of the Internet (N = 275)

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	I use the Internet for study purposes	75	120	18	62	2.76	Agreed
2	To prepare for examinations	114	126	12	20	3.21	Agreed
3	To do my assignments	92	51	90	42	2.70	Agreed
4	To chat with friends	114	96	35	30	3.07	Agreed
5	To watch movies	126	36	68	45	2.88	Agreed
6	To get information	91	114	40	30	2.97	Agreed

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7	To meet new friends	101	114	40	20	3.08	Agreed
8	To improve my reading habit	25	20	86	114	1.73	Disagreed
9	To improve my grades in school	35	50	96	94	2.09	Disagreed
10	To be like others	83	61	48	83	2.52	Agreed

Source: *Researcher's Field Survey*

Key: SA – Strongly Agreed; A – Agreed; D – Disagreed; SD – Strongly Disagreed

Table 2 showed the responses to the reasons for the use of the Internet by the students of Wesley High School Otukpo Benue State. From the analysis, majority of the students agreed with the following reasons for their use of the Internet: for studying purposes (2.76), to prepare for examinations (3.21), to do my assignments (2.70), to chat with friends (3.07), to see movies (2.88), to get information (2.97), to meet new friends (3.08) and to be like others (2.52). However, few respondents that constitute 1.73 and 2.09, respectively, indicated the use of the Internet to improve their reading habit and improve their grades in school.

Research Objective 3: To investigate perceived impact of the Internet facilities on the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State.

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	It enhances my reading ability	20	15	173	67	1.96	Disagreed
2	It makes me active in class	77	138	40	20	2.99	Agreed
3	It increases my reading attention span	20	30	126	99	1.89	Disagreed
4	It helps me to have a better understanding of what I am reading	80	165	10	20	3.11	Agreed
5	Chatting with friends keeps me awake to read in the night	102	138	25	10	3.21	Agreed

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6	Internet articles motivate me to read	63	132	30	50	2.76	Agreed
7	The Internet distracts my reading	113	117	30	15	3.19	Agreed
8	The Internet exposes me to unimportant articles and write-ups	200	30	15	30	3.25	Agreed

Source: Researcher's Field Survey

Key: SA – Strongly Agreed; A – Agreed; D – Disagreed; SD – Strongly Disagreed

Table 3 presents responses gotten on the perceived impact of the Internet on the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State. The result shows that out of the eight perceived impact investigated, six were agreed by the majority of the respondents that constitute 2.99, 3.11, 3.21, 2.76, 3.19, and 3.45, mean scores respectively. These impacts agreed by the respondents on item statements 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8, include it makes me active in class, it helps me to have a better understanding of what I am reading, chatting with friends keep me awake to read in the night, Internet articles motivate me to read, the Internet distracts my reading and the Internet exposes me to unimportant articles and write-ups. Furthermore, majority of the respondents disagreed with item statements 1 and 3, which present that, it enhances my reading ability (1.96), and it increases my reading attention span.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the students' reasons for use of internet facilities and students on their reading culture

Statement	N	df	Mean	S.D	R	P-Value	Decision
Students' Reasons for Use of the Internet	275		3.0000	.60302			
students reading culture	275	274	3.1667	.71774	.210	0.512	Not Significant

***p-value is significant at ≤ 0.05 , df: degree of freedom, S.d: standard deviation, R; relationship,*

The result showed the relationship between reasons for the use of internet facilities and reading culture of students. The result showed the mean and standard deviation

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of the variables. Students' reasons for use of internet facilities: 3.00(0.603) and students reading culture is 3.167(0.718). The degree of freedom is 274. The showed that the relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities is linear and weak $R = 0.210 \times 100 = 21\%$. In the same vein, the result further showed that there is no significant relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities and their reading culture as the p -value = 0.512. Since the P -value > 0.05, the hypothesis which state that there is no significant relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities and students reading culture is accepted.

Discussion of findings

The result showed that students in Otukpo Local Government Area make use of internet facilities. The finding corroborates with the earlier studies carried out by Olatokun (2008), Tarimo and Kavishe (2017), which revealed the high use of the Internet among youths and secondary school students. This is because majority of the students has a mobile device with internet facilities, also majority of the schools has internet enable e-library in the school premises. Also, the results showed that students of Wesley High school Otukpo Benue State make use of the Internet for numerous purposes aside to improve their reading habit and grades in school. Consequently, preparation for examinations had the highest mean score of 3.21. The finding of this study in this regard partially corroborates with the work of Luambano and Nawe (2004), which found the use of the Internet by students particularly for academic purposes as hugely influenced by their teachers who give them assignments requiring the use of the Internet. Thus, the studies revealed that students will only use the Internet if work given to them by their teachers requires them to use Internet facilities. In the same vein, the finding has shown different perceived impact of the Internet on the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State. Some of the impacts are positive, such as making them active in class, understand what they are reading, keep them awake to read in the night, and motivates them to read.

However, the negative impacts include the use of the internet distracting their reading, expose them to unimportant articles and write-ups, fails to enhance their reading ability, and failure to increase their reading attention. With these findings, one can deduce that the negative impacts of the Internet outweigh its positive impacts in the case of students of Wesley High Otukpo, Benue State. This study corroborates the earlier works of Davis (2001), Widyanto and Griffiths (2006), Odaci and Kalkkan (2010), and Odaci (2011), which reported that the use of the Internet by the students

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has either a negative impact or no significant impact on student learning performance or other outcomes.

The authors believed that if these young users are educated, they will use the Internet more for educational information resources rather than leisure or entertainment purposes, which will invariably improve their studying and reading culture. The findings of the study also corroborate with the study of Luambano and Nawe (2004), which investigated the use of the Internet by students of University of Dares Salaam and revealed that many of the students were not using the Internet for issues on education but for communication purposes such e-mailing and Face booking.

The study further showed that some students were using Internet services for pornographic viewing, which is an obvious misuse of Internet facility in an academic background, which negatively affects their reading culture and overall academic performance. The negative influence of the Internet as revealed by the above studies may be attributed to the findings of Manda (2005) that majority of students are not aware that Internet is a veritable tool for searching online academic information but rather jump into the Internet for other frivolous purposes.

Finally, the result showed that there is no significant relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities and their reading culture. The implication of this finding is due to the fact students reasons for use internet facilities is not necessarily because of academic purposes but may be for pleasure and socialization such as the use of social media platforms. The result is supported by Luambano and Nawe (2004), which found the use of the Internet facilities by students is not necessarily for academic purposes but for socialization and pleasure while just few uses internet facilities for academic purposes through their teacher's instructions.

Conclusion

A critical look at the Internet could make one believe that it is a blessing to our generation. However, many students are becoming addicted to the Internet as they spend more time playing games or just surfing the net without any particular reasons. Consequently, the time they spend on studying is automatically reduced, which in turn causes lower academic achievement, which could all be attributed to poor reading culture.

Findings of the study have shown that the students make use of the Internet for different reasons. These reasons include for studying purposes, to prepare for

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examinations, to do their assignments, to chat with friends, to watch movies, to get information, to meet new friends, and to be like others. However, the influence of the use of the Internet is various, which include making them active in class, helping them to have a better understanding of what they are reading, chatting with friends keeping them awake to read in the night, Internet articles motivating them to read, the Internet distracting their reading, as well as exposing them to unimportant articles and write-ups.

Based on the findings, the study concludes that the use of the Internet amidst some positive impacts negatively influences the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made to ensure that the use of the Internet positively influences students' reading culture:

1. Management of secondary schools should organize seminars aimed at teaching the students the right use of the Internet to improve their reading culture.
2. Teachers in secondary schools should give assignments to students that will stimulate effective use of the Internet for academic purposes and improvement of reading culture.
3. School authorities and parents should closely monitor the Internet sites their students and wards visit to ensure that the utilization of the educational sites is encouraged.
4. There should be a law stipulating the age limit of the utilization of some Internet sites that are detrimental to the reading culture of the secondary school populace.
5. Secondary school students should be provided with adequate guidance on how to promote their reading culture through the appropriate use of the Internet.
6. Establishing, equipping and proper maintenance of school libraries as a means of improving the reading culture of the secondary school students should be highly considered and made a priority for all secondary schools

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References

- Acılar, A. (2011). Exploring the aspects of digital divide in a developing country. *Issue Informing Science and Information Technology*, 8, 231-244.
- Akande, S. O. & Bamise, O. F. (2017). The role of school library in academic motivation of Secondary school students in Osun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Library Science*, 6(1), 18-27. DOI:10.5923/j.library.20170601.03.
- Almasi, M., Machumu, H., & Zhu, C. (2017). Internet use among secondary schools students and its effects on their learning. In *INTED2017 Proceedings* (pp. 2379-2390). IATED.
- Chambo, F. F., Laizer, L. S., Nkansah-Gyekye, Y., & Ndume, V. (2013, July). Towards the development of mobile learning model for Tanzania secondary schools: Case study Kilimanjaro region. In *2013 Pan African International Conference on Information Science, Computing and Telecommunications (PACT)* (pp. 127-130). IEEE.
- Chen, Su-Fen & Fu, Yang-Chin (2009). Internet use and academic achievement: Gender differences in early adolescence. *Adolescence*, 44(176), 797-812.
- Davis, R. A. (2001). A cognitive-behavioural model of pathological Internet use. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 17, 187–195.
- Downes, T. (2002). Children's and families' use of computers in Australian homes. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 3(2), 182–196.
- Edeole, I. M. & Adejoke, A.M. (2016). Promoting reading habit among secondary school students in Lagos State: the role of library and ICT. *Asian Journal of Education and e-Learning*, 4(5), 145-152.
- Fuchs, T., & Woessmann, L. (2004). *Computers and student learning: Bivariate and multivariate evidence on the availability and use of computers at home and at school* (No. 1321). CESIFO working paper.
- Jibrin, M.A., Musa, M N. & Shittu, T. (2017). Effects of Internet on the academic performance of tertiary institutions`students in Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Training*, 2(2), 57-69.
- Kolawole, C.O.O. (2005). The state of reading in some selected secondary schools in South Nigeria: A preliminary report. *Issues in Language, Communication and Education: A Book of Readings in Honour of Caroline A. Okedara*. Ibadan: Constellations Books.

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- Kuhlemeier, H., & Hemker, B. (2007). The impact of computer uses at home on students Internet skills. *Computers & Education*, 49, 460–480.
- Luambano, I. & Nawe, J. (2004). Internet use by students of the University of Dares Salaam. *Library High Tech News*, 21(10), 13-17.
- Manda, P. A. (2005). Electronic resource usage in academic and research institutions in Tanzania. *Information development*, 21(4), 269-282.
- Mtega, W. P., Dulle, F. W., Malekani, A. W., & Chaila, A. M. (2014). Awareness and use of Web 2.0 technologies in sharing of agricultural knowledge in Tanzania. Knowledge Management and E-Learning. *International Journal (KM&EL)*, 6(2), 188-202.
- Nnadozie, C.O. & Egwim, F.O. (2010). Analysis of reading habits of pupils in selected public and private primary schools in Owerri, Nigeria. *Madonna Journal of Research in Library and Information Science*, 1(1), 8-22.
- Nwagwu, E. W., Adekannbi, J., & Bello, O. (2009). Factors influencing use of the internet: A questionnaire survey of the students of University of Ibadan, Nigeria. *The electronic library*, 27(4), 718-734.
- Odaci, H. (2011). Academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination as predictors of problematic Internet use in university students. *Computers & Education*, 55, 1614.
- Odaci, H., & Kalkan, M. (2010). Problematic Internet use, loneliness and dating anxiety among young adult university students. *Computers & Education*, 55, 1091–1097.
- Olatokun, W. M. (2008). Internet access and usage by secondary school students in a Nigerian Municipality. *South African journal of libraries and information science*, 74(2), 138-148.
- Sahin, Y. G., Balta, S. & Ercan, T. (2010). The use of Internet resources by university students during their course projects elicitation: A case study. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 9 (2), 234-244.
- Saka, K.A, Bitagi, A.M & Garba, S.K. (2012). Promoting reading culture in Nigerian children. *Nigerian School Library Journal*, 11(2), 13-21.
- Sife, A. S, (2013). Internet use behaviour of cybercafé users in Morogoro Municipality, Tanzania. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 60, 4150.

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- Tarimo, R. & Kavishe, G. (2017). Internet access and usage by secondary school students in Morogoro Municipality, Tanzania. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 13 (2), 56-69.
- Widyanto, L., & Griffiths, M. (2006). 'Internet addiction': A critical review. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 4 (1), 31–51.
- Yani, S. (2003). Reading habits of senior secondary school students in Zaria local government area. *Zaria Journal of Librarianship*, 6 (1&2), 30-49.
- Yebowaah, F. A. (2018). Internet use and its effect on senior high school students in Wall Municipality of Ghana. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 1(1).
- Yusuf, F. (2007). Repositioning school libraries in Nigeria: The catalyst for promoting reading habits among primary and secondary school students. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Yusuf, H. O. (2015). Assessment of teachers' attitude towards the teaching of reading in primary schools in Kaduna metropolis. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 10(1).